

SPCHS SURGICAL VIDEO

How to repair a Mitral Arcade in a small infant?

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Summary:

Hammock mitral valve (MV) repair is historically technically difficult with a guarded prognosis . Surgical experience is extremely limited and variable outcomes are reported. The perioperative strategy and technical details of hammock MV repair in a small infant who presented with severe mitral stenosis are described.

The term hammock mitral valve was first coined by in 1976 by Carpentier , because of the unique appearance of mitral valve apparatus from its left atrial aspect as viewed during cardiac surgery . This anomaly is characterized by enlarged and elongated papillary muscles connected to each other and to the free edge of the anterior mitral leaflet by a bridge of fibrous tissue. The almost absence of chordae tendinea between the fibrous bridge and anterior leaflet results in the fibrous continuity that interferes with the valvular motion and prevents normal apposition of leaflets.

The features of anomalous mitral valve arcade are:

- (1) A near normal mitral valve orifice
- 2) short, thick, and poorly differentiated chordae tendinea with direct attachment of the papillary muscles to the anterior mitral leaflet
- (3) narrow interchordal spaces

(4) few relatively well developed chordae attached to the posterior papillary muscle.

The papillary muscles which are large and elongated are connected to each other and to the free edge of the anterior mitral leaflet by a bridge of fibrous tissue.

The natural history of the malformation is characterized by progressive worsening of valvular regurgitation, stenosis or both.

This 2.5-month-old baby presented with feeding difficulty, recurrent respiratory infections. Echocardiography showed tight mitral stenosis of mitral arcade/ Hammock variety with mitral inflow gradient of 19 mmHg. There was an associated moderate size VSD as well.

SURGICAL VIDEO LINK

<https://youtu.be/IB81OKJrbY8>

Surgical repair of this anomaly is technically challenging, particularly in small infant like this, primarily because of their size, as well as limited surgical field exposure, presence of immature and fragile leaflet tissues or lacking effective subvalvar apparatus.

Repair is performed using, excision/ incision of inter-connecting bridging fibrous bands between chordae / papillary muscles, excision of tethering bands between papillary muscles and ventricular walls, commissurotomy, modified annulus shortening techniques if needed and balanced papillary muscle spitting if needed. Post repair mitral valve size adequacy and competency is checked. Associated defects, like VSD, are repaired as well . Learning objective: Meticulous attention paid to the pathologic morphology of the defect can help enormously in achieving satisfactory surgical outcome.

References:

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